

The Evolution of Photography: From Camera Obscura to Digital Cameras- A Timeline

Photography has made its way into every aspect of everyday life. From cooking to dating, there are few things that don't have a photographic representation. The first known photograph was taken in 1826 by Joseph Nicéphore Niépce using a camera obscura. This technology used light energy to produce an image on a piece of paper or glass.

Since then, photography has undergone many changes, from the introduction of digital cameras, to the invention of social media platforms like Instagram. To get a better understanding of how photography has evolved over time, photographer [Chatz Schwab](#) offers you a timeline of the major milestones over the past 200 years.

The Early Years of Photography

- 1826: The first ever photograph was taken by Joseph Nicéphore Niépce using a camera obscura.
- 1839: Louis Daguerre achieved the first successful major photographic process, naming it the daguerreotype.
- 1841: John Herschel makes the first known recording of stars through a telescope in the southern hemisphere.
- 1851: Isaac Newton demonstrates silver nitrate's ability to create light sensitive images when exposed to light during his experiments with solarized paper.
- 1890s: Alfred Ritz creates mass production of dry plate film and gelatin dry plates for photography.

The advent of digital cameras

Digital cameras are one of the most significant changes that have occurred since the invention of photography. The first digital camera was developed in 1975 by Steven Sasson at Eastman Kodak. It was revealed to the public for the first time in January of 1977, and had an image resolution of 0.01 megapixels.

However, it took more than 20 years for digital cameras to become popularized with photographers. In 2000, Nikon introduced its D1 camera, which recorded images at a resolution of 2.45 megapixels. This new technology led to a drastic increase in sales for Nikon, as well as for other brands that quickly began releasing their own versions of digital cameras with higher resolutions.

Today, many smartphones come equipped with an integrated camera that records photos at high resolutions. As the popularity of smartphones continues to grow, this will likely become one of the most significant changes yet to occur since photography's invention 200 years ago!

The rise of social media

Social media's influence on photography is undeniable. In fact, the use of social media as a marketing tool has increased by 130% in the past three years and continues to grow.

Social media platforms like Instagram and Facebook have changed the way we interact with one another and how we share our lives with others. The rise of these websites has also affected how we communicate visually. With just a few clicks, we can take a photo and share it with our friends and followers all over the world.

A study done by Adweek found that 75% of people wouldn't post an update to their social media account unless they felt their life was interesting enough. That means that 25% of people post less frequently because they feel like their life isn't exciting enough for social media.

This is a major change from how people used to communicate visually. In the past, before the invention of these types of websites, human beings had to depend on mail or phone calls to stay connected with friends and family that were far away. And before cameras became widespread, photography was still largely considered as a form of art rather than as a way for people to document their lives through snapshots.

The proliferation of social media has led to an increase in photo-taking

Conclusion

Photography has been an integral part of human culture for over a hundred years, and it's been changing as technology has advanced. In this blog post, we'll look at a timeline of the evolution of photography from cameras obscura to digital cameras, and discuss how the rise of social media has changed photography.